

I beam-to-RHS column joints with threaded welded studs. An analytical model for the joint resistance

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ABSTRACT

In the current situation of global warming, with increasingly frequent extraordinary climate events, it is important to propose solutions that contribute to more sustainable construction. In this context, having easily executable, demountable, and reusable joints that provide sufficient load-bearing capacity and reasonable stiffness is a very interesting option in the construction of steel-framed buildings. With this main idea, this research work presents innovative bolted beam-to-column joints involving IPE beams and hollow section columns. To avoid difficulties associated with the access to the inside of the tube, in order to tight ordinary bolts, threaded studs welded to the external column face are used instead. The threaded studs can be used in combination with angle cleats connected to the beam flanges to assembly demountable joints. In this paper, a large experimental campaign over full-scale joints is used to validate an analytical model based in the component method to determine analytically the resistance and the failure mode of these type of beam to column bolted joints. Good concordance was observed between the analytical model and test results, allowing to support its suitability for the joint design.

Keywords: Sustainable construction, bolted joints, welded studs, tubular steel structures

1 INTRODUCTION

In the current situation of global warming, with increasingly frequent extraordinary climate events, it is important to propose solutions that contribute to more sustainable construction because construction industry is a significant contributor to global warming and other impacts on the environment. One alternative solution to welded joints in steel structures is the use of bolted joints allowing demountable buildings to achieve a more sustainable construction. The use of bolted joints allows the potential to disassemble the joints, so the buildings can be deconstructed (1) allowing the separation of pieces for their recovery and their reuse. An efficient solution in steel building structures is to combine an open section (typical IPE) as beams with a rectangular hollow section (RHS) as the columns. Nevertheless, the use of bolted joints involving hollow sections presents the problem of accessing the interior of the tube to tight the bolts. To avoid this inconvenience some solutions as the use of blind bolts (2, 3) have been proposed in the past. A cheaper and easy to execute solution that allow the joint to be demountable is the use of threaded studs that are welded to the frontal face of the tube. The welding process only requires a simple stud welding gun. This type of connection was firstly proposed by Maquoi (4, 5), and then has been studied by Vandegans et al. (6), Neves et al. (7) and Serrano et al. (8, 9).

This paper is focussed on the strength of beam-column joints in which the column are rectangular hollow sections, and the beams are open sections. Threaded studs welded to the tube face are used in combination with unequal side angle cleats that are connected to the beam flanges to assembly

demountable joints. The studs connect the column with the short leg of the top and seat angle cleats, while the long leg of the angle cleats is connected to the beam flanges by means of standard bolts. The unified European code of design for steel structures (10) includes the component method as an analytical way to characterize the joints, providing some equations to calculate the stiffness and the strength of joints between open-section profiles. Nevertheless, the joints between open-section beams and hollow-section columns are not covered by the code. As an attempt to bridge the detected gap, this paper proposes an analytical model to evaluate the strength of IPE-beam to hollow section column joints with welded studs through the component method. The resistance of the basic components has been calculated using adapted equations from Eurocode 3 where possible, while for the tube's key components new equations have been developed. A large experimental campaign has been used to validate the proposed component-based model reaching quite good concordance.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

A large experimental campaign was designed to have enough data to validate the analytical equations. So, thirteen full-scale beam-column joint tests were carried out. One of the aims of these tests was to plot the moment-rotation curves from which to obtain the moment resistance of the joints. Two joint main configurations were considered: a beam connected to the column just to one side (SMS) and two beams connected to both sides of the column (DMS). *Fig. 1.* shows these two configurations.

Fig. 1. Joint configuration. (left) beam on side SMS. (right) beam on both sides DMS

Both, the SMS and DMS joints consist of either a square (SHS) or rectangular (RHS) hollow section column with a length of 900 mm and beams with a cross-section HEB 200 or IPE 300 and two different lengths of 840 mm for SMS and 470 mm for each beam in case of joints DMS. Beam and column are joined together by angle cleats of unequal sides L 120x80x10, which connect the flanges of the beam to the frontal face of the column. Any angle cleat was fixed to the beam by 4 metric threaded bolts of M16 and class 8.8, and to the column by 2 welded threaded studs with a reduced diameter on the non-threaded area. In SMS joints with a metric thread M16, class K800 (8MnSi7) and 40 mm in length. For DMS joints the studs were 16 mm in diameter, grade 4.8, and 35 mm in length. The combinations of section for beams and columns together with the β value as the relationship between the beam width and the column width are included in *Table 1.* The table also presents the depth, width and thickness of columns (h_0 , b_0 , t_0) and the lever arm (z) that is defined later.

Table 1. Beam and column sections for joints SMS and DMS. Dimensions of columns and lever arm

Joint	Column + Beam	β	h_0 [mm]	b_0 [mm]	t_0 [mm]	z [mm]
SMS 1	SHS 200.6 + HEB 200	1	200.38	200.58	5.66	246.56
SMS 2	SHS 200.8 + HEB 200	1	200.25	200.17	7.62	246.56

SMS 3	SHS 200.10 + HEB 200	1	200.17	200.08	9.76	246.56
SMS 4	SHS 200.6 + IPE 300	0.75	200.38	200.58	5.66	344.97
SMS 5	SHS 200.8 + IPE 300	0.75	200.25	200.17	7.62	344.97
SMS 6	SHS 200.10 + IPE 300	0.75	200.17	200.08	9.76	344.97
SMS 7	RHS 200.150.6 + IPE 300	1	200.25	150.41	5.58	344.97
SMS 8	RHS 200.150.8 + IPE 300	1	200.00	150.25	7.75	344.97
SMS 9	RHS 200.150.10 + IPE 300	1	200.00	151.00	9.77	344.97
DMS 1	SHS 200.8 + HEB 200	1	200.25	200.17	7.62	246.56
DMS 2	SHS 200.6 + IPE 300	0.75	200.38	200.58	5.65	344.72
DMS 3	SHS 200.8 + IPE 300	0.75	200.17	200.83	7.62	344.72
DMS 4	RHS 200.150.8 + IPE 300	1	200.08	150.17	7.74	344.72

During the welding process of the studs to the tube faces, a ceramic ferrule RF16 was used to protect the molten weld pool. *Fig. 2* shows details of the of the angle cleats with the hole position and the distances to frontal and lateral edges that were in accordance with those specified by Eurocode 3 (10). The thickness was 10 mm and the measured yield stress of the angle cleats was $f_{y,l} = 319 \text{ MPa}$. The bolts were tightened using a torque of 190 Nm, in two stages. First, a torque of 150 Nm was applied, then in a second stage, the torque objective of 190 Nm was reached.

Fig. 2. Details of the angle cleats and distances from holes to edges

The experimental program also included some specific tests carried out on individual studs under tension and under shear. For the tension tests, see *Fig. 3*, two stud diameters M16 and M20 combined with two classes of studs: 4.8 and K800, were welded to short pieces of tubes in opposite faces, to obtain their resistance under tension load. The same three tube thicknesses of 6, 8 and 10 mm, that were used in the beam-column joint configurations were considered, so a set of twelve specimens combining the two diameters, and classes of studs and the three tube thicknesses were tested.

Fig. 3. Tension tests of studs welded to the tubes.

For the shear tests a pair of studs were welded on both faces of an intermediate plate with the same thickness as the diameter of the stud. Two external plates with half thickness were connected to each side of the intermediate plate by means of the studs in a double shear configuration. Six specimens were prepared to obtain the resistance of the studs under shear combining two stud diameters of M16 and M20, two studs classes of 4.8 and K800 and two options regarding the dimensions of the hole to accommodate the weld collar. Thus, counterbored specimens, to make wider the side of the hole in which the collar weld is located and specimens with a constant diameter in the holes were tested.

3 MODEL FOR JOINT RESISTANCE

The moment resistance of the full joint when it is under bending moments can be calculated from the resistance of the weakest basic component, according to Eq. (1).

$$M_R = F_R \cdot z \quad (1)$$

Where F_R is the resistance of the weakest basic component of the joint and z is the lever arm of the joint, measured from the mid plane of the horizontal flange of the lower angle cleat to the upper row of studs (Fig. 1). The basic components that were identified related with the studs included: the studs in tension, in shear or under a combination of tension and shear, the punching shear in the frontal face of the column. Other identified components were the flange cleat in bending and the lateral face of the column under compression. Additionally, the failure of the lateral faces under shear (section 3.4) should be assessed in a different way, by considering for the resistance the shear forces in the column below and above the beam-column connection.

3.1 Resistance of studs

The equations of Eurocode 3 for bolts were adapted to calculate the resistance of the welded studs. Several loading conditions that include studs in tension, in shear, lamellar tearing of the studs, studs in combined tension and shear and punching shear in the frontal face of the column were considered. Eq. (2) gives the resistance of studs in tension, $F_{t,Rd}$. The partial safety factor γ_{M2} that was assumed to be 1.0 in this study in order to contrast with the experimental results.

$$F_{t,Rd} = \frac{0.9 \cdot f_{u,s} \cdot A_s}{\gamma_{M2}} \quad (2)$$

where:

A_s is the reduced area of the stud,
 $f_{u,s}$ is the ultimate strength of the stud,

Eq. (3) allows to calculate the resistance of the frontal face of the column under punching shear, $B_{p,Rd}$.

$$B_{p,Rd} = \frac{0.6 \cdot \pi \cdot d_2 \cdot t_0 \cdot f_{y,0}}{\gamma_{M2}} \quad (3)$$

where:

d_2 is the reduced diameter of the stud,
 t_0 is the thickness of the column,
 $f_{y,0}$ is the yield stress of the column,

Eq. (4) gives the resistance of the stud under laminar tearing, $F_{lt,Rd}$.

$$F_{lt,Rd} = \frac{\pi \cdot d_2^2 \cdot f_{y,0}}{\gamma_{M2}} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (5) allows to calculate the shear resistance of the stud, $F_{v,Rd}$. The coefficient a_v is variable with the type of the stud. When the shear plane passes through the threaded area: $a_v=0.6$ for class 8.8 and $a_v=0.5$ for class 4.8. But $a_v=0.6$ if the shear plane passes through the unthreaded area.

$$F_{v,Rd} = \frac{a_v \cdot f_{u,s} \cdot A_s}{\gamma_{M2}} \quad (5)$$

where:

- a_v is a coefficient variable with the type of the stud,
- $f_{u,s}$ is the ultimate strength of the welded stud,
- A_s is the reduced area of the stud,

For a combination of tension and shear, the resistance of welded studs is calculated according to Eq. (6) where $F_{v,Ed}$ is the applied shear,

$$\frac{F_{v,Ed}}{F_{v,Rd}} + \frac{F_{t,Ed}}{1.4 F_{t,Rd}} \leq 1 \quad (6)$$

where:

- $F_{v,Ed}$ is the applied shear,
- $F_{v,Rd}$ is the shear resistance of the stud,
- $F_{t,Ed}$ is the applied tension,
- $F_{t,Rd}$ is the tension resistance of the stud

3.2 Resistance of angle cleats

When designing bolted connection, to model the design resistance of the flange angle cleat in bending an equivalent T-stub in tension may be used (11). The failure of a T-stub flange can occur in three different ways: mode 1 that assume a complete yielding of the flange, mode 2 assuming a combination of bolt failure with yielding of the flange and mode 3 assuming just a bolt failure.

For a failure mode under complete yielding of the flange (mode 1), Eq. (7) gives the design resistance of the T-stub flange $F_{T,1,Rd}$. In this equation, m is a factor that takes into account the positions where the yielding of the flange may appear. Depending on the distance between beam and column, it could be in the long or in the short leg of the angle cleat. The positions are showed in Fig. 4.

$$F_{T,1,Rd} = \frac{4 \cdot M_{pl,1,Rd}}{m} \quad (7)$$

where:

- $M_{pl,1,Rd}$ is the moment when complete yielding of the flange occurs, see Eq. (8),
- m geometry-factor

Eq. (8) allows the calculation of $M_{pl,1,Rd}$ assuming an equivalent T-stub with an effective length $l_{eff,1}$ equal to 0.5 times the length of the angle cleat.

$$M_{pl,1,Rd} = \frac{\sum l_{eff,1} \cdot t_l^2 \cdot f_{y,l}}{4 \cdot \gamma_{M0}} \quad (8)$$

where:

- t_l is the thickness of the cleat,
- $f_{y,l}$ is the yield stress of the angle cleat,
- γ_{M0} is the partial safety factor

Fig. 4. The geometry-factor m variable with the distance between beam and column. (left) distance higher than $0.4 t_l$ and (right) distance lower or equal to $0.4 t_l$

In case of a mode 2 failure assuming a combination of bolt failure with yielding, the design resistance $F_{T,2,Rd}$ was calculated with Eq. (9).

$$F_{T,2,Rd} = \frac{2 \cdot M_{pl,2,Rd} + n \sum F_{t,Rd}}{m + n} \quad (9)$$

where:

$M_{pl,2,Rd}$ is the moment that produces the yielding of the flange and can be calculated with Eq. (10),

n is the distance from the stud-axis to the border of the leg as showed in Fig. 4,

$F_{t,Rd}$ is the tension resistance of studs,

m is defined in Fig. 4

Eq. (10), allows the calculation of $M_{pl,2,Rd}$ assuming an equivalent T-stub with an effective length $l_{eff,2}$ equal to 0.5 times the length of the angle cleat.

$$M_{pl,2,Rd} = \frac{\sum l_{eff,2} \cdot t_l^2 \cdot f_{y,l}}{4 \cdot \gamma_{M0}} \quad (10)$$

where:

t_l is the thickness of the cleat,

$f_{y,l}$ is the yield stress of the angle cleat,

For failure in mode 3 that assumes just the stud failure, Eq. (11) gives, the resistance of the welded studs $F_{T,3,Rd}$.

$$F_{T,3,Rd} = \sum F_{t,Rd} \quad (11)$$

where:

$F_{t,Rd}$ is the resistance of individual welded studs

Considering the equations included in this section, the design tension resistance of the T-stub flange is obtained as the minimum value of Eq. (7), Eq. (9) and Eq. (11). Thus, this combined condition is written by Eq. (12). It is important to notice that prying effects are implicitly taken into account when determining the design tension resistance of $F_{T,1,Rd}$, $F_{T,2,Rd}$, and $F_{T,3,Rd}$.

$$F_{T,Rd} = \min (F_{T,1,Rd}, F_{T,2,Rd}, F_{T,3,Rd}) \quad (12)$$

3.3 Resistance of the lateral face of the column under compression

The resistance of the lateral face of the column in compression was calculated according to Eurocode 3, (10) approaches, but adapting the equations for open-sections to take into account the fact that in the tubular column there are two lateral faces. This methodology has been proposed in (12). Eq. (13) allows to calculate the mentioned resistance of the lateral face $F_{L,c,Rd}$. In this equation, ω is a reduction factor to introduce the interaction between compression and shear. This factor ω is variable with the transformation parameter β_T that can be obtained from table 5.4 in Eurocode 3 (10). Then the factor ω can be obtained for different values of β_T according to Eq. (14). The coefficient ω_1 is obtained by Eq. (15) and the effective width of the lateral face by Eq. (16).

$$F_{L,c,Rd} = \frac{2 \cdot \omega \cdot b_{eff} \cdot t_0 \cdot f_{y,0}}{\gamma_{M0}} \quad (13)$$

$$\omega = \begin{cases} \omega_1, & \text{if } \beta_T = 1 \\ \omega_1 + 2(1 - \beta_T)(1 - \omega_1), & \text{if } 0.5 < \beta_T < 1 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where:

$$\omega_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + 1.3 \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot b_{eff} \cdot t_0}{A_v} \right)^2}} \quad (15)$$

$$b_{eff} = 2t_l + 0.6r_l + 5(t_0 + 2.4t_0) \quad (16)$$

where

- t_l is the thickness of the angle cleat,
- r_l is the radius of curvature of the angle cleat,
- A_v is the shear area of the column,
- t_0 is the thickness of the column,
- $f_{y,0}$ is the yield stress of the column,
- γ_{M0} is the safety factor once again equal to 1.0

3.4 Resistance of the lateral face of the column under shear

The resistance of the lateral face of the column under shear was also calculated according to the Eurocode 3 (10) approaches for open sections. This resistance $V_{L,Rd}$ is obtained by Eq. (17).

$$V_{L,Rd} = \frac{0.9 \cdot A_v \cdot f_{y,0}}{\sqrt{3} \cdot \gamma_{M0}} \quad (17)$$

where:

- A_v is the column shear area,
- $f_{y,0}$ is the column yield stress
- γ_{M0} is the safety factor, taken as 1.0

3.5 Resistance of the frontal face of the column in bending

The resistance of the frontal face of the column in bending was obtained by adapting an approach initially proposed in (13) that has been applied by the authors for welded beam-column joints in (14) with satisfactory results. Eq. (18) presents the proposal in which the effective length for one stud-row in tension L_{eff} can be calculated according to Eq. (19).

$$F_{f,Rd} = \frac{2 \cdot t_0^2 \cdot L_{eff} \cdot f_{y,0}}{b_0 \cdot (1 - \beta)} \quad (18)$$

$$L_{eff} = 2 \cdot b_0 \cdot \sqrt{1 - \beta} \quad (19)$$

where

- β is the ratio of the distance between the studs and the width of the column
- b_0 is the width of the column,
- t_0 the thickness of the column,
- $f_{y,0}$ is the yield stress of the column

4 COMPARISON MODEL vs. TEST

4.1 Validation of equations for welded studs in tension

The maximum load $F_{u,exp}$, obtained during the tension test for the studs welded to the tubes (Fig. 3), for each stud-tube assembly based on stud diameter, quality of the stud, and the thickness of the tube is presented in Table 2. In this table also the analytical resistance of the welded stud in tension $F_{t,Rd}$, from Eq. (2), the resistance of the frontal face of the tube under punching shear, $B_{p,Rd}$, from Eq. (3), and the analytical resistance of the studs under lamellar tearing, $F_{lt,Rd}$, from Eq. (4) are presented. The mechanical properties of the studs were taken from previous studies carried out by the authors (15). Another column shows the ratio of the experimental to the analytical resistance of the stud, $R_{s,Rd}$, taken as the minimum of $F_{t,Rd}$, $B_{p,Rd}$, $F_{lt,Rd}$. Table 2 also includes the thickness of plate (t_0), the reduced diameter of the stud (d_2), the ultimate strength of the stud ($f_{u,s}$) and yield stress of the column ($f_{y,0}$).

Table 2. Test results and analytical predictions for studs in tension

Specimen	$F_{u,exp}$ [kN]	$F_{t,Rd}$ [kN]	$B_{p,Rd}$ [kN]	$F_{lt,Rd}$ [kN]	$\frac{F_{u,exp}}{R_{s,Rd}}$	t_0 [mm]	d_2 [mm]	f_{us} [MPa]	f_{y0} [MPa]
S16-4.8	51.1	62.2	51.5	62.3	0.99	5.54	13.2	505.2	373.9
S16-4.8	73.7	62.2	70.9	62.3	1.18	7.62	13.2	505.2	373.9
S16-4.8	75.2	77.8	104.6	68.7	1.09	9.76	13.2	631.9	430.6
S16-K800	54.3	79.2	54.2	64.2	1.00	5.58	13.2	643.1	390.5
S16-K800	71.6	79.2	74.0	64.2	1.12	7.62	13.2	643.1	390.5
S16-K800	-	65.8	104.0	68.4	-	9.77	13.2	534.4	428.0
S20-4.8	43.3	97.2	65.8	97.4	0.66	5.66	16.5	505.2	373.9
S20-4.8	83.8	97.2	88.6	97.4	0.95	7.62	16.5	505.2	373.9
S20-4.8	119.8	121.6	130.7	107.4	1.12	9.76	16.5	631.9	430.6
S20-K800	47.1	101.8	67.0	98.6	0.70	5.66	16.5	529.2	380.8
S20-K800	-	101.8	91.8	98.6	-	7.75	16.5	529.2	380.8
S20-K800	121.1	119.3	130.1	106.9	1.13	9.77	16.5	619.7	428.0

A good agreement between tests and proposal is observed from the table with most of the results on the safety side, an average safety factor of 0.95 and an average deviation of 16%.

4.2 Validation of equations for welded studs under shear

The maximum load for one stud under shear $F_{V,exp}$ obtained from the shear tests and the presence or not of a counterbored hole is presented in Table 3. In this table also the analytical resistance of the welded stud under shear $F_{v,Rd}$ obtained from Eq. (5) and the ratio of the experimental to the analytical resistances are presented.

Table 3. Test results and analytical predictions for studs under shear

Specimen	Counterbored	$F_{v,exp}$ [kN]	$F_{v,Rd}$ [kN]	$\frac{F_{v,exp}}{F_{v,Rd}}$
S16-4.8	Yes	86.5	93.4	0.93
S16-4.8	No	87.5	93.4	0.94
S16-K800	Yes	115.5	127.0	0.91
S16-K800	No	115.5	129.9	0.89
S20-4.8	Yes	133.5	126.5	1.05
S20-K800	Yes	172.0	189.9	0.91

Again, good agreement between test results and analytical proposal were observed allowing to validate the models. A maximum error of 13%, an average deviation 8.13% and an average safety factor of 0.94 was found. Therefore, the shear resistance of the studs can be determined with common equations for the shear failure of bolts by considering as surface under shear the corresponding of the weld collar and the actual mechanical properties of the welded studs in that area.

4.3 Validation of moment resistance

Table 4 presents the experimental moment resistance $M_{R,EXP}$ of the thirteen joints tested for their comparison with analytical results. The resistance of the basic components of the joint was assessed using Eq. 1. To proceed a fair comparison between experimental and analytical results it is important to take into account that from the experiments, the observed ultimate failure mode was punching (P) in case of joints involving a tube thickness of 6 mm or a failure on the stud (S) in tension for thicknesses of 8 mm or 10 mm. Therefore, Table 4 presents also the analytical moment resistance

$M_{R,AN}$ but without considering those analytical results in which the failure was on the angle cleat or on the frontal face of the tube, that is, taking only into account the punching failure or the studs failure. The predicted failure mode and the ratio between the experimental and the analytical moment resistance are also included in the *Table 4*. A general good agreement is observed both to the moment resistance and to the predicted failure mode.

Table 4. Test results and analytical predictions for moment resistance and failure mode.
P: punching shear, S: stud, T: tension, V: shear

Joint	$M_{R,EXP}$ [kNm]	$M_{R,AN}$ [kNm]	Failure	$M_{R,EXP}/$ $M_{R,AN}$
SMS 1	22.14	24.81	P	0.89
SMS 2	34.71	36.45	P	0.95
SMS 3	31.66	31.72	S	1.00
SMS 4	30.37	34.72	P	0.87
SMS 5	40.99	50.86	S (V+T)	0.81
SMS 6	41.34	42.53	S (V+T)	0.97
SMS 7	38.02	34.26	P	1.11
SMS 8	36.61	50.94	S (V+T)	0.72
SMS 9	38.51	42.67	S (V+T)	0.90
DMS 1	17.94	21.06	S (V+T)	0.85
DMS 2	31.68	25.74	S (V+T)	1.23
DMS 3	26.28	25.75	S (V+T)	1.02
DMS 4	29.03	25.75	S (V+T)	1.13

Taking into consideration the Eurocode 3 classification for strength, only joint SMS7 is classified as a partial-strength joint. The others are classified as nominally pinned as their design moment resistance is lower than 0.25 times the moment resistance of the connected beam. In terms of stiffness the joints showed a semi-rigid behaviour as proved by the authors (8).

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

In this piece of research, the resistance of bolted beam-column joints based on welded studs and angle cleats and connecting IPE beams to hollow section columns has been studied. The results of a large experimental campaign have been used to validate some simplified analytical models based in the component method. Based on this research, some conclusions are outlined:

- The resistance of the studs was evaluated by using equations for bolts. In the calculations, the mechanical properties of the welded zones were used in combination with the reduced diameter of the studs. When using these mechanical properties, the results were close to the experimental values.
- A new component-based analytical model for strength, able to reproduce both failure modes and resistance moments of the joints has been proposed.
- When designing joints with a thin column, the behaviour of the joint is governed by the yielding of the frontal face while their collapse is produced by the punching shear of the frontal face of the column at the row of the studs under tension.
- When designing joints with a thicker column, the behaviour of the joint is governed by the angle cleats, while their collapse is produced by the breakage of the studs.
- Easily removable joints must be designed with tight tolerances to be removable by hand. However, joints formed by 6 mm thickness columns presents a noticeable deformation of their frontal face when the yield is exceeded. Further investigations must be done in order to this deformation be quantified to ensure an easy re-assembly of their components.

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